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Adoption of Agricultural Digital Services by Smallholder Farmers in the Central and Southern Zones of Senegal

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Abstract

The use of digital services offers numerous benefits to agricultural value chain actors including smallholder farmers. However, knowledge gaps exist on the adoption of digital services in agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa. In this context, a survey was conducted to identify the determinants of farmers using digital agricultural services in the central and southern zones of Senegal. Descriptive analyses and simple logistic models were used to identify types of digital services farmers use and the key factors influencing their adoption. Overall, 30% of the sampled used digital agricultural services with the most frequently used services in order of importance being: rainfall forecasts (30%), cumulative rainfall (28%), and market information (7%). Other services such as online training (4%), air temperature forecasts, wind intensity and direction (3%), rainfall breaks (2%), flood risks (2%), seasonal forecasts (1%), out-of-season rainfall (1%) and wet sequences (1%) were rarely used in the two study sites. Highlighted adoption determinants included training in good agricultural practices, sensitization to digital services, and awareness of a producer who uses these services. Millet and cowpea producers were reported to be less likely to use digital agricultural services than those who do not grow one or other crops. By contrast, producers who grow maize are more likely to use digital services than non-maize growers. Finally, the higher the TLUs (Tropical Livestock Units) the producer owns, the more likely they are to use agricultural digital services. Young people and male producers are also more likely to use digital agricultural services.

Keywords: agricultural digital services, adoption, Senegal

1. BACKGROUND

Agriculture is the cornerstone of economies and livelihoods in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), contributing about 30 % to the region's Gross Domestic Product. The sector provides direct and indirect employment to 70% of the population in the region thus is inexplicably linked to household food security (Mazaya et al., 2024). Sub-Sahara Africa is endowed with the largest area of arable uncultivated land in the world, abundant natural resources and a youthful population (FAO and ITU, 2022). The region has a food insecurity paradox, prevalent cases of food insecurity and malnutrition despite possessing abundant resources to become a net surplus producer of food commodities. This can be attributed to a wide range of factors including climate change, land degradation (Sakho-Jimbira and Hathie, 2020), poor value chain coordination and limited access to extension services, appropriate agricultural inputs and equipment, financial services and

markets. Digital agriculture is viewed as one of the key drivers for sustainably transforming African agriculture in line with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through improved uptake of agricultural technologies, optimisation of resources and reduced transaction costs and information asymmetries.

Senegalese agriculture has undergone significant changes in recent decades, from agricultural systems initially focused on subsistence and family to strong orientation towards cash crops and production for different markets of crops traditionally considered subsistence such as maize, rice, cowpea and millet (African Development Bank, 2022). Globally, subsistence production intended mainly for household consumption has been dominant in most developing countries since time immemorial. However, the global community is increasingly promoting improved value chain coordination and market oriented agriculture as part of efforts to sustainably transform local food systems and address the underlying causes of food insecurity for smallholder farmers.

Indeed, many farms are no longer limited to self-consumption agriculture but rather to a mixed form of self-consumption and market-oriented agriculture. This paradigm shifts places farms in a market-based and value-for-money approach. However, the business environment in agricultural value chains in Senegal, like other countries in SSA, is characterized by several constraints that do not facilitate this agribusiness approach for producers. These include poor access to quality agricultural inputs, mainly certified seed with a utilization rate of 14% (case of rice, maize, and groundnut) and mineral fertilizer with a level of use of 25% (DAPSA, 2020), low access to training, poor access to market and tangible information. In addition, there are difficulties in accessing information on agricultural services, including training services, extension services, weather information and commodity prices. Despite producers' innumerable difficulties in accessing these agricultural services, many service providers have emerged in recent years.

To overcome these difficulties of information asymmetry, several innovations to digitize agricultural value chains have appeared on the market with the objective of reducing these constraints and making agricultural products and services more accessible. These include climate information systems, market information systems, and e-commerce of inputs and outputs. Improved market penetration of digital innovations in agriculture can be attributed to the Senegalese government's efforts to modernize the agriculture sector through the adoption of policies and action plans like the Emerging Senegal Plan (2019 - 2023) and the Digital Senegal Strategy (2016 -2025) (FAO and ITU, 2022).

Digital services if made inclusive offer opportunities for value chain actors including those in rural communities to achieve sustainable livelihoods by improving efficiency and creating income generation opportunities along agricultural value chains. However, knowledge gaps exist on the extent access and uptake of digital services among smallholder farmers. This study seeks to investigate the extent of use and factors affecting adoption digital services among smallholder farmers in the central and southern zones of Senegal. Results are presented and discussed in three sections: use of digital services (Section 3.1), presentation of model results including adoption factors (Section 3.2), and test about the predictive power model (Section 3.3).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1.Data collection

The data were collected from a socio-economic survey during May and June of 2021 in seven administrative provinces of Senegal namely: Saint Louis, Louga, Thiès, Fatick, Kaolack, Kolda, and Sédhiou. The sampling and data collection consisted of a stratified three stage survey with the following stages: selection and administering of questionnaires to (i) 10 producers' organizations (POs); (ii) 19 municipalities covered by these producer organizations. and 803 producers who were members of these organizations. A team of eight investigators, including two supervisors, surveyed the provinces over 15 days. The investigators and supervisors were trained over a period of 3 days, including one day of practice in the field. The ODK collect tool was used for the deployment of the questionnaire on tablets.

2.2. Method of statistical and econometric analyses

We used the logistic regression model (LRM) to analyze the factors associated with adopting agricultural digital services. The LRM allows us to measure the association between the occurrence of an event (the use of digital services) and factors potentially influencing the event. The explanatory variables were selected based on the literature review and the study's basic assumptions.

The logistic regression model (logit) is written as follows:

$$P(Y = 1 | X_i) = \frac{1}{(1 + e^{-X_i\beta})}$$

Where:

- P represents a conditional probability.
- X_i the explanatory variables and,
- β the vector of the coefficients.

The values taken by Y and X of the model are assumed to be known and the model looks for the values of the coefficients. This specification requires the probability of belonging to be a linear combination of explanatory variables. The conditional expectation is then given by:

$$E(Y|X_1 = x_1, X_2 = x_2, \dots, X_k = x_k) = L(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-X\beta}}$$

The coefficients of the logistic model allow us to know only the direction of the effect. To refine the analysis, we used the Odds Ratio (OR) to give both the direction and the magnitude of the effect of the explanatory variable on the dependent variable.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Use of digital services

Digital services used by the surveyed producers were: a) meteorological information, b) agricultural market trends for inputs and outputs and c) online agricultural training. In our sample, 30% of producers paid for digital services with 99 % of these producers who paying for meteorological services (Figure 1). While regarding market information, 14% of users (or 7% of the overall sample) used that service. Lastly, only 6 % of digital services users accessed training courses through digital technologies (4% of the overall sample).

Meteorological information accessed by , producers comprised information on rainfall forecasts, cumulative rainfall, temperature forecasts, wind (intensity and direction), seasonal forecasts, rain breaks, flood risks, off-season rains, and wet sequences. Information on rainfall forecasts and cumulative rainfall forecasts, particularly in volume, were the most used among the digital services, with 30% and 28%, respectively. This can be attributed to the prevalence of rain-fed agricultural systems in Senegal. The majority of small-scale producers rely heavily on rainfall to carry out cultivation operations including soil preparation, sowing, irrigation, fertilization and phytosanitary treatment. Other types of digital services are rarely used as shown in Figure 2. However, it is important to note that flood information is more used in the Kolda region. It is in the region with significant rice production in this study. Rice is very sensitive to flooding It can undergo second germination due to pouring when rice tillers fall back to earth because of the importance of nitrogen in the leaves, high plant density and under the effect of the wind.

3.2. Presentation of model results

The estimated model is significant according to the likelihood ratio test at all conventional levels of statistical significance (Table 1). The significance test carried out on the coefficient estimators shows that various parameters significantly impact the use of digital services. These parameters used were sex, age, training on good agricultural practices, awareness of the use of agricultural digital services, neighboring producers, cultivation system, area sown, production objective, availability of rain gauges, and the Tropical Livestock Unit Index (TLU).

3.2.1. Socio-demographic factors

The likelihood of using digital services decreases with age. Indeed, one more year on the producer's age reduces his chance of using agricultural digital services by 3%, all other things being equal. In other words, young farmers tend to use digital services more than older farmers. These results are similar to those presented by previous research (Shang and al., 2021; Barnes and al., 2019). However, Pivoto et al. (2019) observed that using autopilot spraying resulted in quite different results, with older people being likelier to use this technology.

When considering gender, women are 56% less likely to use digital services than men. Thus, according to the model's results, being a woman rather than a man reduces her chances of using agricultural digital services by 56%. This corroborates with findings from previous research on gender disparities associated with access to information among farming communities in Senegal (Diouf et al., 2019)

Knowing another producer who uses digital services increases the farmer's chances of using these services by 202%, *ceteris paribus*. This concurs with other research findings which reported external pressure from the community and environmental organizations to contribute positively to technology adoption (Aubert and al., 2012; Lynne and al., 1995).

Training in good agricultural practices influences the use of agricultural digital services. In fact, producers benefiting from these types of training are three (3) times more likely to use agricultural digital services than other producers, all other things being equal. Through their study on the adoption of new technologies in agriculture, Aubert and al. (2012) showed that farmers with a high level of education can better understand the application of new technologies. Although our work involves training in good agricultural practices and not formal education, the effect of on-the-job training could be equated with that of formal education. Indeed, producers who have been trained would be more aware of the stakes of certain parameters on productivity, in particular, the importance of the right sowing dates and the consideration of global meteorological factors in their decision-making process.

All other things being equal, producers who have been made aware of digital services in agriculture are 2.54 times more likely to use these services than other non-beneficiary producers. According to Pino and al. (2017), farmers who think technology is beneficial tend to adopt it. Because awareness-raising on agricultural digital services generally focuses on the added value of these services in productivity, sensitized farmers would be more informed of the benefits of these services than non-sensitized ones.

3.2.2. Economic factors

According to model estimates, cultivating 1 hectare more increases farmers' chances of using digital services by 108%. Similar studies have produced similar results (Shang et al., 2021) indicating that the size of the operation is positively linked to the adoption of digital services. Similarly, Tamirat et al. (2017) argue that large farms can benefit from economies of scale and are more likely to be able to afford the high initial investment of new technologies.

Farmers who produce maize are 2.07 times more likely to use digital services than those who do not grow maize, *ceteris paribus*. As previously mentioned, the common digital services used by farmers include rain forecasts and rainfall accumulations. Maize cultivation is water demanding and very sensitive to water stress compared to several other cereals because of its poor root system. In contrast, farmers who produce millet are 75% less likely to use agricultural digital services than other producers who do not grow millet, all other things being equal. Similarly, producers who cultivate cowpeas are 77% times less likely to use agricultural digital services than producers of other crops. Indeed, millet is a dry cereal, and its sowing can be done in the dry seedbed. Thus, producers do not often need useful rain (about 20 mm or more) to sow. As for the cowpea, it is a short-cycle, water-inefficient species whose water needs are easily covered in a relatively short growing period. According to Isgin et al. (2008), biophysical conditions such as yield variability and locations are important in technology adoption. Indeed, the variability in maize yield under water stress for the species studied would be greater than that of millet and cowpea.

Livestock composition was synthesized through a composite indicator of livestock assets (or TLU). According to the model results, having one more TLU increases the farmer's chances of using agricultural digital services by 108%. Indeed, it is important to note that the digital services used by producers in this study were not specifically designed for livestock farming, even though nomadic herders can use them to

identify points where it is possible to graze animals. In any case, this indicator would reflect more on the socio-economic level of farmers. In other words, this correlation suggests that the richest farmers are more likely to use digital services. Other studies on the determinants of digital services adoption have not all converged on the same result. Lambert et al. (2015) found a positive relationship between livestock ownership and the adoption of a computerized management system. However, Shang et al. (2021) did not find significant correlation between livestock ownership and technology adoption.

3.2.3. Farmers' perception and availability of meteorological equipment

The availability of rain gauges promotes producers' adoption of agricultural digital services. Indeed, producers with fields close to a rain gauge (within a radius of 5 km) are 3.45 times more likely to use digital services than other producers whose fields are more than 5 km from a rain gauge. The model results show that variables related to farmers' perceptions, including utility and ease of use, are insignificant.

3.3. Predictive power of the model

Using 0,5 as the classification threshold, the model presents a predictive power of 83% with a specificity of 92%. In other words, as shown in Table 2, the model correctly classifies 92% of individuals who have not used agricultural digital services as not having used them. In contrast, the sensitivity being 62% suggests that the estimate correctly classifies 62% of those who have used agricultural digital services as having used them. The receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) gives us an area between the bisector and the curve of 0.89 (figure 3). This indicates that the model has good predictive power.

4. CONCLUSION

This study shows a relatively low and limited use of agricultural digital services among farmers. Available services mainly include meteorological information, agricultural market trends, and training, with meteorological services, particularly rain forecasts and cumulative rainfall, being the most commonly used. Several factors are associated with the adoption of digital services, including age, gender, training in good agricultural practices, awareness of digital tools, peer influence, availability of a rain gauge, size of the sown area, cultivation system, and herd size.

Farmers who grow maize are more likely to use digital services than those who do not, while those producing millet or cowpea are less likely. Larger sown areas and higher livestock holdings are also linked to a greater likelihood of using digital services. These findings indicate that service providers need to adjust their targeting strategies by considering these factors. Improving network coverage remains an important lever for increasing adoption among farmers.

The likelihood of adopting digital services declines with age, with each additional year reducing the probability of use by 3%, all other factors being equal. Younger farmers therefore tend to use digital services more than older ones. Gender disparities are also significant, with women being 56% less likely than men to use digital services. Peer influence plays a strong role, as knowing another producer who uses digital services increases the likelihood of adoption by 202%.

Training in good agricultural practices also increases the probability of using digital services, with trained farmers being three times more likely to adopt them compared to untrained farmers. While the training provided focuses on agricultural practices rather than formal education, it appears to enhance farmers' understanding and decision-making, particularly in relation to sowing periods and the integration of meteorological factors.

Awareness campaigns about agricultural digital services are another important driver of adoption. Farmers who have been sensitized to these services are 2.54 times more likely to use them than those who have not. By highlighting the role of digital services in improving productivity, awareness-raising efforts contribute to better informing farmers and promoting the use of available technologies.

In conclusion, a strategic approach that integrates improvements in service delivery, infrastructure development, and farmer capacity building is required to foster a broader adoption of digital services in the agricultural sector. Strengthening these dimensions is likely to facilitate the effective incorporation of digital tools into agricultural practices and contribute to the modernization of farming systems. Sustained efforts to align digital service provision with farmers' needs and local conditions will remain essential to ensuring long-term adoption and impact.

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Figure 1. Type of digital services used by producers

Source: Authors' computations

Figure 2. Subcategories of digital services used by producers

Source: Authors' computations

Figure 1. Receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC curve)

Source: Authors' computations

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TABLE 1. MODEL ESTIMATION

Variable	Odds ratio (dy/dx)	Coefficient	Significance
Sex (female)	0,444 (-0,096)	-0,810	*
Age	0,974 (-0,003)	-0,026	*
Instruction (knowing to read and write.)	0,700 (-0,040)	-0,355	
Agricultural training (trained)	3,001(0,142)	1,099	***
Knowing a digital service user	2,024 (0,085)	0,705	*
Sensitization (aware)	2,543 (0,127)	0,933	*
Perceived usefulness (useful)	1,978 (0,076)	0,682	
Perceived ease			
easy	2,378 (0,099)	0,866	
don't know	1,569 (0,048)	0,450	
Insurance (assured)	1,183 (0,020)	0,168	
Cultivated area	1,075 (0,008)	0,072	*
Grow			
Rice	0,769 (-0,030)	-0,262	
Maize	2,076 (0,088)	0,730	*
Millet	0,248 (-0,179)	-1,393	***
Peanut	0,673 (-0,48)	-0,395	
Cowpea	0,335 (-0,114)	-1,092	*
Rain gauge (Available)	3,447 (0,164)	1,237	***
Tropical Livestock Unit (TLU)	1,082 (0,009)	0,079	*
Harvest destination			
Self-consumption	0,517 (-0,083)	-0,657	
Sale	0,674 (-0,51)	-0,394	
cons	0,547	-0,603	
Pseudo R2		0,386	
AIC		337,7	
BIC		420,9	
p		7.09e-29	

*** p<0,01 ; ** p<0,05 ; * p<0,1

Source: Authors' estimations

TABLE 2. LEVEL OF SENSITIVITY AND SPECIFICITY OF THE MODEL

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Classified	True		Total
	+	-	
+	74	21	95
-	46	249	295
Total	122	271	390
Sensitivity	61.67%		
Specificity	61.67%		
Correctly classified	82 %		

Source: Authors' estimations